

ASSIGNMENT

CENSUS OF INDIA

SUBMITTED TO: DR. PREETI MAHAJAN

PROF. DEPARTMENT OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION
SCIENCE.

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M.LIB. 1ST SEMESTER

ROLL NO.- 2

PREFACE

The Population Census has been a major source for collecting data pertaining to the population count of the country, its composition and other features. In this huge exercise requiring massive resources, maintaining the quality - both in terms of coverage and content - is a challenging task and deficiencies and errors can't be ruled out.

2. The Census Organisation has the tradition of evaluating the results of the Population Census through Post Enumeration Surveys (PES), known also as Post Enumeration Checks (PEC). Such surveys have been conducted every time after each Census since 1951. Its main objective is consciously to quantify the omission and duplication in the census enumeration as well as to measure the response errors in respect of certain selected characteristics canvassed in the census. The results of the PES are important in throwing light to the areas of census operations which would need attention including the concepts and definitions employed, procedures of enumeration and related instructions to the field staff etc. This is of help in improving conduct of future census operations. It may be mentioned here that no attempt has been made in the past or is being made now to adjust the Indian census results based on the PES results.

3. The PES Report of 2011 Census presents detailed analysis of the results along with the objective and organization of the survey, its methodology, schedules canvassed for PES. The planning, designing of the schedules, preparation of manual of instructions for the field staff, training of supervisory staff, processing and tabulation of the data, analysis of the results and the preparation of the Report have all been done by the Demography Division of the Organisation. The data entry work was done in the DataProcessing Division. The training to the field staff and canvassing of the schedules were the responsibility of the Directorate of Census Operations of the state and union territories. Taking into consideration, the recommendations of National Statistical Commission (NSC) for enhancing the credibility and faith in Census operations, efforts were made to entrust field work of PES to the staff of Directorate of Economics & Statistics (DES) in all States/UTs. Accordingly, in most of the States/UTs the field work was conducted by the statistical staff of DES. Only in very few States, where DES staff were not able to handle the entire work, staff of Directorate of Census Operations also conducted field work jointly.

4. I would express my thanks to the Directors of Census Operations, the officers of

Directorates of Economics and Statistics of the respective state governments and other government organisations for working hard in completing the survey in the stipulated time schedule. I would also like to record the sincere efforts put in by Dr. D. K. Dey, Additional Director, Shri S.C.L. Meena Deputy Director, Shri R. Chakravarty, Assistant Director (Retd.), Shri Undurthy Chantibabu Murthy, S.I.Gr.-II, Shri Deepak Kumar, Compiler for completion of the work of the PES. I would also like to appreciate the contributions of Data Processing Division for processing the data and providing the relevant tables based on the PES. The entire work was completed under the overall guidance of Shri Deepak Rastogi, Additional Registrar General, India.

New Delhi
July, 2014

Dr.C.Chandramouli
Registrar General & Census Commissioner, India

CENSUS OF INDIA

AUTHORITY:

TITLE	CENSUS OF INDIA
PUBLISHER	OFFICE OF REGISTRAR GENERAL & CENSUS COMMISSIONER
PLACE OF PUBLICATION	NEW DELHI
1 ST CONDUCTED	1872
1 ST PUBLISHED	1881
LATEST (15 TH EDITION)	2011
FREQUENCY	10 YEARS

INTRODUCTION:

The Indian Census is the most credible source of information on Demography (Population characteristics), Economic Activity, Literacy and Education, Housing & Household Amenities, Urbanization, Fertility and Mortality, Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes, Language, Religion, Migration, Disability and many other socio-cultural and demographic data since 1872. Census 2011 is the 15th National Census of the Country. This is the only source of primary data in the village, town and ward level, It provides valuable information for planning and formulation policies for Central and the State Governments and is widely used by National and International Agencies, Scholars, business people, industrialists, and many more.

HISTORY:

The Indian Census has a rich tradition and enjoys the reputation of being one of the best in the world. The first Census in India was conducted in the year 1872. This was conducted at different points of time in different parts of the country. In 1881 a Census was taken for the entire country simultaneously. Since then, Census has been conducted every ten years, without a break.

SCOPE:

- Census of India is a document of National Importance.
- Data is collected through survey.

2011 census: the gigantic task of census taking was completed in two phases. In the first phase, known as House-listing Operations, conducted between April to June, 2010 in different States and UTs, all building and structures, residential, partly residential or non-residential were identified and listed and the uses to which they were put recorded. Information on houses, household amenities and assets were also collected. In the second phase, known as Population Enumeration, conducted from- 9th to 28th February 2011 with 5 days revisional round from 1st to 5th March, 2011 gives more detailed information on each individual residing in the country, Indian national or otherwise, during the enumeration period was collected.

- It covers 28 States, 7 Union Territories, 640 Districts, 5,961 Sub-Districts, 8,001 towns, 6,40,852 villages.
- It provides information regarding Demography (Population Density, Population Size, Sex Ratio), Education (Literacy Rate), Houses and Assets.
- It provides valuable information to governments for planning and policies formulation.

TREATMENT

- Data is presented in statistical form, maps, charts and tables are given.
 - It is divided into two parts
 - ✚ THE NATIONAL POPULATION REGISTR (NPR): It is a register of the usual residents of the country.
 - ✚ PROVISIONAL POPULATION TOTALS: These shows information in Maps, Charts and Tables.
- There are also annexure of tables in all series providing information related to:
- Decadal Population Growth in between 2001-2011.
 - Density of Population.
 - Sex Ratio.
 - Population in the Age Group 0-6.
 - Literates.
- Tables on Houses, Household Amenities and Assets-Slum Households .

- Tables on Houses, Household Amenities and Assets- Scheduled Casts.
- Tables on Houses, Household Amenities and Assets- Scheduled Tribes.
- Annexure is given.

ARRANGEMENT:

The Census 2011 is in geographical order. It provides statistical information about States/ Union Territories from North to South i.e firstly Jammu & Kashmir, then next Himachal Pradesh, then Punjab and so on and lastly Andaman & Nicobar Islands.

It is available in 35 Volumes(one volume per state). Each volume is arranged in the following order:

- Size, Growth rate and Distribution of population.
- Density of Population.
- Gender composition of the Population.
- Literacy rate.

FORMAT:

It is available in both printed and electronic form.

PRINT FORMAT:

- It is available in hard binding.
- The print and font is readable.
- The paper is thick.
- Colored maps, tables and charts are given of all states, UTs and districts.

ONLINE FORMAT:

- The Data is available at <http://www.censusindia.gov.in>
- The data can be easily download.
- PDF format is available. PDF of Census District Manual can be downloaded easily.
- Digital library is available.
- Population finder.

CD-ROM is available.

CONCLUSION:

The Indian census has not been a mere statistical operation and the data collected is not only properly scrutinized at different levels but also presented with cross classification of various parameters for interpretation and analysis in an interesting manner. It may be seen from the history of Indian Census that how the changes have taken place from one census to other depending upon the need of the time, country and also demand of the data users and development of technology. The Indian census is well recognized for the data it reveals. Problems relating to political, social and cultural reasons also makes it challenging. In spite of all these difficulties, the census in India is being conducted since 1871 uninterruptedly.

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